

envision

D7.4 FINAL REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869366.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	869366	Acronym	ENVISION	
Full Title	Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation			
Start Date	1 st September 2020	Duration	36 months + 3-month extension	
Project URL	https://envision-h2020.eu/			
Deliverable	D 7.4: Final report on dissemination activities			
Work Package	WP7: Dissemination and Communication			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31. 10. 2023	Actual	25. 10. 2023
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	ITC			
Responsible Author	Ms Aleksandra Kocet			
Contributions from	Mr. Vassilis Spitadakis (ETAM)			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
D1.0	25. 10. 2023	Draft	Final draft prepared for review	Ms Aleksandra Kocet (ITC)
D2.0	10. 11. 2023	Draft	Input received from partners	Mr. Vassilis Spitadakis (ETAM)
F1.0	13. 11. 2023	Final	Integration of input	Ms Aleksandra Kocet (ITC)

Disclaimer

This document and its content reflect only the author's view, therefore the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains!

CONTENT

Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Dissemination and communication tools and activities	6
2.1 ENVISION website	6
2.1.1 Website measurements	7
2.2 Social Media	9
2.2.1 ENVISION LinkedIn page	12
2.2.2 ENVISION Twitter page	13
2.2.3 ENVISION Facebook page	14
2.2.4 ENVISION YouTube channel	15
2.2.5 ENVISION SlideShare	17
2.3 ENVISION e-Newsletters	18
2.4 EuroGEOSS showcase	20
2.5 Hackathon	21
2.6 Meetings with developers, open-source communities	22
2.7 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	23
2.8 Project events (seminars/workshops)	25
2.9 Policy session – Panta Rhei Conferences	28
2.10 Clustering event	28
2.11 External events	30
2.12 Presentations/attending at International Conferences	31
2.13 PR articles published in national/regional/European press	31
2.14 Publications in business journals	32
2.15 Scientific and Technical publications	33
2.16 White Papers and Testimonials	33
2.17 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	42
3 Outcome of Dissemination Efforts: Commercial Leads and Impact	43
4 Analysis of results	45
5 Conclusions	46

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Number of visitors and page views 8

Table 2: Social Media Channels 10

Table 3: Followers/subscribers on the social channel 10

Table 4: Number of posts on social channels 11

Table 5: Meetings with developers, open-source communities..... 23

Table 6: Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders 23

Table 7: External events attended by ENVISION project partners..... 30

Table 8: PR articles published in national/regional/European press 31

Table 9: Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions 43

Table 10: Potential ENVISION customers 43

Table 11: Key Performance Indicators 45

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The ENVISION home page before 7

Figure 2: The ENVISION final home page..... 7

Figure 3: Example of WP Statistics for July 2023 9

Figure 4: LinkedIn followers analytics..... 13

Figure 5: ENVISION Twitter account analytics 14

Figure 6: ENVISION Facebook account analytics 15

Figure 7: ENVISION YouTube channel..... 16

Figure 8: ENVISION views of videos on YouTube 16

Figure 9: ENVISION SlideShare analytics..... 18

Figure 10: ENVISION Newsletter #5 19

Figure 11: ENVISION Newsletter #5 analytics 20

Figure 12: Presentation of ENVISION solutions on the hackathon 22

Figure 13: Agenda for Clustering event 29

Figure 14: The second White Paper provided by NOA 36

Figure 15: The third White Paper provided by NOA 38

Figure 16: The fourth White Paper provided by EV ILVO..... 41

Executive Summary

ENVISION work package 7 (WP7) covers the project's dissemination, communication and results exploitation. WP7 has been coordinated by ITC, and all ENVISION partners have been committed to raising awareness, engaging external stakeholders and then disseminating and exploiting the project's results.

The core objective of work package 7 was to disseminate key findings and outcomes of the project in a structured manner to maximise project impact and outreach across key stakeholder groups during and after the end of the project.

This document has been prepared to report the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities performed all along ENVISION project life and to describe the means that have been used to facilitate the widespread of information and knowledge from the results created by the project, among and beyond the consortium members.

The main WP7 objectives were the following:

- Regularly updating ENVISION website
- Regularly publishing posts on ENVISION social channels
- Monitoring the project website and social media accounts
- Publishing newsletters
- Regularly meeting with a different target audience
- Participating in different external events and conferences at the national and European level
- Organizing project events to raise visibility for the project
- Publishing articles in national, regional, and European press
- Scientific and technical publications
- Coordinating partners for all these activities for better and stronger involvement in dissemination and promotional activities

Deliverable “D7.4 Final report on dissemination activities” is the updated version of the “D7.3 Draft report on dissemination activities.”

This final report includes the dissemination and communication activities in the frames of WP7 of the ENVISION project from May 2023 to the end of October.

It also summarises and analyses the achievements of the entire ENVISION project for dissemination and communication executed by the Consortium.

1 Introduction

The goal of this Work Package was to effectively communicate and disseminate knowledge and know-how throughout the ENVISION project and beyond.

The dissemination and communication plan was really ambitious, with several communication tools and tasks to do. The Communication Strategy was designed to help the project partners communicate effectively to achieve the project's core objectives.

This is how the decision to create a form on JotForm (<https://form.jotform.com/210193573145048>) proved to be very successful. With the help of a pre-prepared form, the partners reported on their dissemination and communication activities in a quick and efficient manner.

So, the WP7 leader had a clear view of dissemination and communication activities that have been done.

For systematic monitoring, we have used "ENVISION DC Toolbox" – based on Excel spreadsheets, always updated with the information from JotForm's.

2 Dissemination and communication tools and activities

Most of the activities have been performed during the period from the 1st of March 2022 until the end of May 2023. All these have also been reported in the deliverable D7.3.

This report presents the last activities performed from June to the middle of October. This deliverable also summarized all dissemination and communication activities done through the 3 years of the project duration.

2.1 ENVISION website

The ENVISION website (<https://envision-h2020.eu/>) serves as the primary interface for communication with the public and is regularly updated to provide various essential information to visitors.

The ENVISION website has been operational since the inception of the project and is regularly updated by the webmaster. Project partners contribute to the content updates, ensuring that the information remains current and relevant.

In May 2023, a restructuring process was initiated, beginning with the home page. The aim was to revamp the website to align it more closely with the project's commercial offerings.

The final enhancement has been done in the last months of the project. The focus is on making the project's offerings immediately visible to potential users or customers.

We can say the ENVISION project employs a well-structured and user-friendly website as the primary channel for public communication. Regular updates and a clear organization of information aimed at commercial relevance reflect the project's commitment to effective communication with its target audience.

Figure 1: The ENVISION home page before

Figure 2: The ENVISION final home page

2.1.1 Website measurements

The ENVISION website has garnered significant attention, receiving 33.155 visitors and 61.262 page views in total. This indicates a substantial increase in web traffic, especially during events and newsletter releases.

Website traffic is monitored using WP (Word Press) Statistics. It provides detailed information about the browser, search engine, and most popular content (categorized by tags, categories, and authors) of our website’s visitors. This data is invaluable for assessing the website's performance and user engagement.

Data are collected monthly and provide data on user interactions with the site. For a better overview, the data are provided in the table below.

Table 1: Number of visitors and page views

C1: Number of visits to the project website		
Date	Visitors	Page Views
29/1/2021	116	9
28/2/2021	204	373
31/3/2021	227	374
30/4/2021	161	291
31/5/2021	184	379
30/6/2021	204	413
31/7/2021	327	273
31/8/2021	626	376
30/9/2021	350	289
31/10/2021	777	1315
30/11/2021	903	1589
31/12/2021	958	1572
31/1/2022	1539	2849
28/2/2022	2056	4428
31/3/2022	1344	2999
30/4/2022	982	1947
31/5/2022	988	1782
30/6/2022	992	1811
31/8/2022	894	3217
30/9/2022	1244	2582
31/10/2022	1344	2912
30/11/2022	1330	2500
31/12/2022	1330	2500
31/1/2023	1338	2517
28/2/2023	1288	2513
31/3/2023	1489	2842
30/4/2023	1255	2424
31/5/2023	2645	1399

30/06/2023	1595	3215
31/07/2023	1503	3040
31/08/2023	1209	2519
30/09/2023	1427	3029
20/10/2023	873	1740
Total	33.155	61.262

Figure 3: Example of WP Statistics for July 2023

The KPI for project website visits has not only been met but surpassed.

2.2 Social Media

ENVISION's social media channels aim to disseminate project updates, engage with a broader audience, and establish collaborations with related initiatives, especially in the Earth Observation-based sector.

Hashtags that are being used are the following:

[#earthobservation](#) [#agriculture](#) [#sustainable](#) [#environmental](#) [#monitoringsystem](#) [#payingagency](#) [#co designing](#) [#cocreation](#) [#farms](#) [#farming](#) [#agritech](#) [#innovation](#) [#certifications](#) [#certifyingbodis](#).

Table 2: Social Media Channels

Social Media Channel	Direct Link
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC7a4V9GgwQhPAneqnmqmsxQ
SlideShare	https://www.slideshare.net/EnvisionH2020

We gather data on our followers and posts each month across all our social channels. The data presented in the table shows that the number of followers is increasing every month, which proves that the content we publish is interesting for our target audience.

Table 3: Followers/subscribers on the social channel

C3: Followers/subscribers on social networks					
Date	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	SlideShare	YouTube
30/9/2020	79	28	35		
31/10/2020	114	43	55		
31/11/2020	128	44	58		
31/12/2020	133	46	59		
29/1/2021	190	49	65		
28/2/2021	217	66	68		
31/3/2021	238	76	73		
30/4/2021	249	87	80		/
31/5/2021	262	89	81		/
30/6/2021	277	102	82		/
31/7/2021	296	115	84		/
31/8/2021	300	118	86		/
30/9/2021	308	125	89		3
31/10/2021	322	130	94		6
30/11/2021	333	143	101		12
31/12/2021	354	144	104		15
31/1/2022	431	148	125	0	15
28/2/2022	454	158	126	0	20
31/3/2022	474	169	131	0	22
30/4/2022	476	173	132	1	23
31/5/2022	487	178	137	1	23
30/6/2022	489	186	136	1	23
31/8/2022	502	187	144	1	23
30/9/2022	507	194	144	1	23
31/10/2022	533	203	145	1	24
30/11/2022	565	230	148	2	25

31/12/2022	565	230	148	2	25
31/1/2023	568	233	149	2	25
28/2/2023	579	242	149	2	25
31/3/2023	581	245	149	2	25
30/4/2023	599	260	150	2	25
31/5/2023	600	265	150	2	24
30/06/2023	615	273	151	2	25
31/07/2023	621	278	154	2	25
31/08/2023	622	283	153	2	25
30/09/2023	627	291	158	2	26
20/10/2023	630	298	158	2	26

Table 4: Number of posts on social channels

C3: Posts on social networks				
Year	Month	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook
2020	September	16	8	3
	October	22	0	3
	November	6	0	0
	December	8	1	0
2021	January	18	2	1
	February	15	7	4
	March	19	5	6
	April	19	10	5
	May	19	9	6
	June	10	11	5
	July	12	3	2
	August	8	1	2
	September	9	9	4
	October	8	5	2
	November	15	4	5
	December	7	5	4
2022	January	14	10	5
	February	6	9	4
	March	10	14	4
	April	4	3	1
	May	13	8	1
	June	4	4	1
	July	4	5	4
	August	1	4	1
	September	6	5	0
	October	16	29	13
	November	7	12	8
	December	7	12	8

2023	January	3	4	1
	February	10	11	6
	March	6	6	2
	April	2	1	1
	May	9	6	1
	June	8	8	3
	July	2	3	2
	August	2	2	1
	September	2	3	1
	October	2	3	2
	Total:	349	242	122

ENVISION's social media strategy is comprehensive, leveraging multiple platforms to reach a diverse audience. The project's consistent presence on these platforms ensures that its objectives, activities, and outcomes are widely known and have a lasting impact on the community.

2.2.1 ENVISION LinkedIn page

ENVISION's LinkedIn page serves as the project's primary professional networking platform. It is an effective tool for the project's exploitation strategy and promoting ENVISION results. The platform targets potentially interested Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies.

ENVISION project gained 630 followers and published 349 different posts.

Figure 4: LinkedIn followers analytics

2.2.2 ENVISION Twitter page

The ENVISION Twitter account is used to establish collaborations with EU initiatives related to Earth Observation.

As of mid-October, the account had 298 followers and followed 196 accounts, including similar projects, initiatives, and organizations. The account has posted 242 tweets, mainly focusing on collaborations and project updates.

Figure 5: ENVISION Twitter account analytics

2.2.3 ENVISION Facebook page

The ENVISION Facebook page showcases the human side of the project, including partners, events attended, and marketing materials.

The page has achieved 158 followers and published 122 posts since the project's inception.

Figure 6: ENVISION Facebook account analytics

2.2.4 ENVISION YouTube channel

The ENVISION YouTube channel hosts promotional videos and other visual content related to the project.

A playlist on ENVISION YouTube provides access to 14 videos and has 26 subscribers.

Figure 7: ENVISION YouTube channel

Vsebina	Ogledi ↓	Čas gledanja (ure)	Naročniki	Prikazi	Razmerje med prikazi sličic in kljki
Skupaj	317	8,7	2	1.546	5,7 %
ENVISION Testimonial by LoginEKO	120 37,9 %	1,5 17,2 %	0 0 %	182	14,3 %
ENVISION services assisting CAP requirements, develop...	39 12,3 %	2,0 22,8 %	0 0 %	251	4,4 %
ENVISION 2nd Clustering Event online, 30 Jun 2023	37 11,7 %	2,1 24,7 %	0 0 %	95	4,2 %
ENVISION Testimonial by Abbey Holman, LEAF	24 7,6 %	0,4 4,2 %	0 0 %	218	2,3 %
ENVISION services in practice - The case of Cyprus an...	22 6,9 %	0,5 6,0 %	0 0 %	233	3,9 %
Earth Observation services in support of agriculture an...	20 6,3 %	1,1 13,2 %	0 0 %	208	3,4 %
ENVISION Testimonial - Csilla Nemet, Project Manager	15 4,7 %	0,2 2,7 %	0 0 %	55	5,5 %
Deep Learning for Event Detection on Grasslands	9 2,8 %	0,5 5,2 %	0 0 %	88	4,6 %
ENVISION - Coproducing Earth Observation based mo...	8 2,5 %	0,1 1,2 %	0 0 %	65	4,6 %
ENVISION project partner NOA_work	8 2,5 %	0,1 0,8 %	0 0 %	25	12,0 %
ENVISION introduction video	6 1,9 %	0,1 0,8 %	1 50 %	56	10,7 %
URDG Team ENVISION WP2	5 1,6 %	0,0 0,5 %	0 0 %	32	12,5 %
BEYOND Centre of the National Observatory of Athens ...	2 0,6 %	0,0 0,2 %	0 0 %	25	8,0 %

Figure 8: ENVISION views of videos on YouTube

2.2.5 ENVISION SlideShare

This communication channel has been used to give access to presentations when they were not available on other sources. With 17 SlideShare's, we achieved a total of 604 views from the SlideShare opening until the middle of October.

SlideShares	Likes	Views	Downloads
An automated end-to-end framework for CAP monitoring, On-demand access to the ENVISION Data cube 7 months ago • 7 slides	0	2	0
An automated end-to-end framework for CAP monitoring - Lessons learned from the Cypriot use case 7 months ago • 21 slides	0	3	0
ENVISION services in practice - The case of Cyprus and the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation (CAPO) 7 months ago • 12 slides	0	7	0
Cultivated Crop Type Maps 11 months ago • 19 slides	0	24	0
Grassland Mowing Events Detection 11 months ago • 30 slides	0	32	0
Analytics on Vegetation & Soil Index time-series and DataCube End Point service 11 months ago • 13 slides	0	49	0
ENVISION Earth Observation services for CAP monitoring.pdf 1 year ago • 18 slides	0	17	0
Identification of organic farming practices.pdf 1 year ago • 17 slides	0	26	0
ENVISION_Business Model approach.pdf 1 year ago • 7 slides	0	19	0
ENVISION: Steps towards developing innovative soil services at a regional scale.pdf 1 year ago • 20 slides	0	15	0
The ENVISION solution.pdf 1 year ago • 12 slides	0	13	0
Beyond Seminars - Deep Learning for fusion of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data and grassland mowing detection.pdf 1 year ago • 54 slides	0	43	3

SlideShares		Likes	Views	Downloads
	EXCELSIOR Workshop_InoSens-1.pdf 1 year ago • 14 slides	0	14	0
	DataCAP Sentinel datacubes, crowdsourced street-level images and annotated.pdf 1 year ago • 28 slides	0	96	0
	Deep Learning Methods for Grassland Activity Monitoring.pdf 1 year ago • 12 slides	0	50	1
	ENVISION Coproducing Earth Observation based monitoring tools for sustainable agriculture 1 year ago • 27 slides	0	123	0
	Envision overview 1 year ago • 6 slides	0	71	0

Figure 9: ENVISION SlideShare analytics

2.3 ENVISION e-Newsletters

The e-Newsletters served as an efficient communication channel to share updates on the project's progress among project partners and external stakeholders.

The newsletters were created using Mail Chimp and are distributed to subscribers who have signed up through a form on the ENVISION website. Once released, e-Newsletters are also uploaded to the project website and shared across social media channels.

The ENVISION e-Newsletters are a testament to the project's commitment to regular periodic communication and engagement with its audience. Through these newsletters, stakeholders could stay updated on the project's progress, achievements, and upcoming activities.

Five e-newsletters have been issued, exactly how it was planned.

The 5th edition of the ENVISION project's newsletter celebrates the successful culmination of a 3-year journey dedicated to advancing sustainable agriculture through Earth Observation solutions and practices. The project has achieved significant outcomes and is committed to continuing to exploit its results.

<https://mailchi.mp/4f0e29a26ed0/envision-newsletter-6191090>

Figure 10: ENVISION Newsletter #5

21 Opened	1 Clicked	5 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
--------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Successful deliveries	82	94.3%	Clicks per unique opens	4.8%
Total opens	32		Total clicks	1
Last opened	10/25/23	4:17AM	Last clicked	10/25/23
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

Most recent campaign performance

[See all campaigns](#)

Figure 11: ENVISION Newsletter #5 analytics

2.4 EuroGEOSS showcase

Several partners from the ENVISION project, including DRAXIS, AGROAPPS, NOA, ETAM, OCS, and ITC, attended the EuroGEOSS workshop held from the 7th to the 9th of December 2022 in Athens.

The ENVISION project, has engaged with EuroGEOSS and its partners in various ways, showcasing its potential impact. Here are some key points to consider regarding the impact of the ENVISION project at EuroGEOSS:

- **Submission to EuroGEOSS:** By submitting an Expression of Intent to EuroGEOSS in 2022, the ENVISION project demonstrated its commitment to the regional initiative's goals, signifying its alignment with the broader European and global efforts for Earth observation and data-sharing.
- **Technical Expertise:** NOA's presentation on the technical aspects of the ENVISION data cube during the workshop highlights the project's capability to contribute valuable insights and solutions related to big satellite image time-series data for agriculture monitoring.
- **Commercialization and Business Development:** The involvement of ETAM in discussions related to the commercialization of the ENVISION project is related to the commercialization of ENVISION products.

- User Involvement: OCS's presentation on how users are involved in testing the ENVISION services underscores the project's commitment to user engagement and feedback, ensuring that the developed solutions meet the real-world needs of stakeholders.
- Collaboration and Networking: Participation in workshops and sessions provided the ENVISION partners with opportunities to network, collaborate, and learn from other organizations and experts involved in EuroGEOSS.

The ENVISION project's participation in the EuroGEOSS showcase was significant. Through multiple presentations and sessions, the project was able to highlight its achievements, objectives, and future plans. This also led to valuable partnerships and knowledge exchange.

2.5 Hackathon

In a groundbreaking collaboration, the ENVISION project teamed up with NASA and CALLISTO for the International SPACE APPS Challenges Hackathon. This event brought together experts, developers, and enthusiasts, challenging them to innovate using free and open data from NASA and its Space Agency Partners.

The hackathon, which attracted a whopping 96 participants, was a significant milestone for the ENVISION project. It provided a unique opportunity to test, validate, and enhance the project's datasets and tools in real-world scenarios. The global attention garnered from collaborating with esteemed institutions like NASA further spotlighted the project's objectives and resources.

The challenge posed by the ENVISION and CALLISTO projects, titled "Services 4 CAP monitoring", was a highlight of the event. Participants were given access to a plethora of data from the projects, including in-situ data, EO-based products, satellite, and street-level imagery. The challenge's objective was to fuse data from multiple sources to extract a crop-type map for a sample area of Cyprus and then visualize the results on a web application. Impressively, one team rebuilt the ENVISION platform using the provided open-source platform code.

Key takeaways from the hackathon include:

- The open-source nature of the ENVISION platform was pivotal, enabling participants to access, modify, and repurpose the code seamlessly.
- The diverse datasets provided a rich foundation for participants, emphasizing the importance of data comprehensiveness and quality.
- Real-world events like this hackathon offer invaluable feedback, revealing areas of improvement that might not be apparent in controlled environments.

Post-hackathon, the insights and innovative solutions presented have immensely benefitted the ENVISION project. The event not only validated the project's direction but also bolstered ENVISION's standing in the open-source developer community.

Figure 12: Presentation of ENVISION solutions on the hackathon

2.6 Meetings with developers, open-source communities

The ENVISION project aimed to foster collaboration and gather insights by engaging with developers and open-source communities. This was achieved through planned meetings, where the project's technical aspects, services, and potential integrations were discussed.

A total of ten meetings with developers and open-source communities were planned.

Twelve of these meetings have been conducted. Here are some notable interactions for the last meeting that has not been reported in deliverable until now.

These meetings have been instrumental for understanding the needs of the developer and open-source communities, and exploring potential collaborations. Engaging with these communities ensured a benefit from the collective expertise of diverse stakeholders.

This proactive approach to engaging with developers and open-source communities has fostered collaboration, gathered valuable insights, and paved the way for potential integrations and partnerships.

Table 5: Meetings with developers, open-source communities

Project Partner	Date	Developers	Meeting description
URDG	14/4/2022	Agtelligence	Meeting between the two projects. Two members from Agtelligence https://www.agtelligence.space/ and 3 URDG and 2 AgroApps ENVISION project members with a plan to explore future collaborations.
AgroApps	6/10/2023	(2 developers from Spotify, 1 Business Analyst from Unisystem, 1 developer from IBM, and 2 developers from Schoox)	The aim of this workshop was to introduce participants to the ENVISION add-on development tool, ensuring they gain a comprehensive understanding of its features, functionalities, and potential applications. The workshop sought to equip developers from diverse organisations with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively integrate and leverage the ENVISION tool in their respective interests.

2.7 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

The ENVISION project partners recognize the importance of direct interactions with stakeholders. These informal person-to-person meetings aim to foster collaboration, gather insights, and understand the needs and feedback of various stakeholders.

The number of scheduled meetings was set at a relatively high level, possibly even exceeding the optimal threshold. Out of the 80 planned informal person-to-person meetings, nearly half of them, totalling 39, were successfully conducted. One of the reasons was definitely the COVID situation.

Table 6: Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
LEAF	10/05/2023	RB Organic	LEAF conducted an interview of RB Organic, the farm that participated in the UK BC/Task 6.5 trial audit.

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			LEAF gathered feedback on the ENVISION platform as well as the farm's perspectives on the use of EO and ENVISION services in environmental assurance systems like LEAF Marque. The farm provided valuable insights on the benefits, opportunities and challenges of using EO in environmental assurance systems.
LEAF	06/06/2023	LEAF Marque Technical Advisory Committee (TAC),	LEAF presented the findings of LEAF's research within the ENVISION project to the LEAF Marque Technical Advisory Committee (TAC), a multistakeholder group that oversees and informs the development of the LEAF Marque Standard requirements. The TAC provided feedback on the use of EO in the LEAF Marque Standard requirements, which will inform LEAF's approach to using EO in the LEAF Marque system and the development of future case studies.
URDG	27/062023	KTM–Agrifood	Yiorgos Gadanakis met with Debbie Tully, KTM–Agrifood, Innovate UK KTN and Pedro Carvalho to discuss the ENVISION services as these are delivered via the platform. In addition, future activities linking EO with the assessment of agriculture in the content of Africa it was discussed.
LEAF	4/05/2023	H2020 ENVISION Panel - Advancing Environmental Monitoring through State-of-the-Art Earth Observation Technologies and Collaborative Initiatives	An interactive session for questions and discussion aimed at exploring recent advancements in ICT-enabled EO-based environmental monitoring. This session focused on integrating principles of EO data sharing, management, and ICT technologies to enhance environmental support in Europe, while also emphasizing the importance of standardisation in environmental monitoring practices. Through a state-of-the-art review, discussion on agri data models and sharing approaches, collaboration with EU initiatives, examination of standardisation efforts, and analysis of best practices,

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			participants gained insights into the latest developments in environmental monitoring and explore effective strategies for leveraging technology, collaboration, and standardisation to address environmental challenges.

2.8 Project events (seminars/workshops)

The ENVISION project planned for each partner to organise and actively participate in events, seminars, and workshops. Project events methodology was prepared to manage these ENVISION events effectively.

The Consortium organised 12 project events, presenting and demonstrating project outcomes and use cases, while some of those events had a policy and cross-fertilisation focus. It was recommended that the organisation of the events follow the specific roles and outcomes assigned to each partner.

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
EV ILVO	07/06/2023	AgriTechDay '23: robotics and AI in agrifood	ILVO has launched the Flanders AgrifoodTEF, the Flemish test and experimentation facility (TEF) in the European Agrifood TEF project. The aim was to accelerate the development of artificial intelligence, data and robotics solutions in the agri-food sector, test them in a realistic agricultural environment and bring them to the market in Flanders and Europe. ILVO will provide services for testing, experimentation, certification and validation. As part of this event, how artificial intelligence and satellite imagery can be used to estimate soil quality parameters was presented (Envision SOC monitoring data product) and feedback was collected to continue to address current needs and showcase the benefits of AI and earth observation in agricultural monitoring.

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
INOS	07/06/2023	Advancing Environmental Monitoring: State-of-the-Art Technologies, Collaborative Initiatives, Standardisation, and Best Practices	<p>This interactive panel discussion bridges the gap between EO and environmental monitoring through ICT, focusing on data sharing, management, and standardisation principles.</p> <p>Agenda: An interactive session for questions and discussion aimed at exploring recent advancements in ICT-enabled EO-based environmental monitoring. This session will focus on integrating principles of EO data sharing, management, and ICT technologies to enhance environmental support in Europe, while also emphasizing the importance of standardisation in environmental monitoring practices. Through a state-of-the-art review, discussion on agri data models and sharing approaches, collaboration with EU initiatives, examination of standardisation efforts, and analysis of best practices, participants will gain insights into the latest developments in environmental monitoring and explore effective strategies for leveraging technology, collaboration, and standardisation to address environmental challenges.</p> <p>14:00 - 14:05: Introduction and Welcome Speaker: Maja Fišić, InoSens [Workshop Organizer]</p> <p>14:05 - 14: 10 : Keynote Presentation Speaker: Farhan Sajito, PRIVANOVA SAS [Expert from the Standardisation Sphere]</p> <p>14:10 - 14: 25 : Perspectives from the Space Agencies Speaker: Representative from the European Space Agency (EASA) or Copernicus [To be announced]</p> <p>14:25 - 14: 50 ENVISION Project Insights</p> <p>a) Overall Architecture - Speaker: Ifigeneia Tsioutsia, AgroApps [ENVISION Project Manager]</p> <p>b) Presentation on the LEAF Marque Standard and Integration of ENVISION Services - Speaker: Abigail Holman, LEAF</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>14:50 - 15:05: Insights from MEF4CAP Findings of MEF4CAP regarding the utilization of digital technologies for monitoring CAP indicators, Nikos Kalatzis, Neuropublic</p> <p>15:05 - 15:25: Panel Discussion An interactive session for questions and discussion aimed at exploring recent advancements in ICT-enabled EO-based environmental monitoring, with a specific focus on integrating principles of EO data sharing, management, and ICT technologies to enhance environmental support in Europe.</p> <p>15:25 - 15:30: Closing Remarks Speaker: Maja Fišić, InoSens [Workshop Organizer]</p>

Project events had an important impact in different ways:

- Knowledge Sharing: At these events, project partners shared their knowledge and presented various aspects of the project.
- Networking: The events facilitated networking with other projects and stakeholders, fostering potential collaborations and partnerships that could extend the project's reach and impact.
- Targeted impact: The events aimed to create targeted awareness among paying agencies, certification bodies, researchers, stakeholders, and local communities, which is expected to facilitate adopting ENVISION's outcomes.

The project events played a significant role in increasing the visibility and awareness of ENVISION, sharing knowledge, fostering commercial discussions, and networking, which collectively contributed to the project's impact.

One of these was definitely participating in Agricultural Exhibition "Ką pasėsi - the largest exhibition for agro-industry innovations in the Baltic States, with around 300 companies and organizations participating. ENVISION's participation in this exhibition allowed the project to present its tools and mobile applications to a large audience of approximately 70,000 visitors over three days.

Most frequent visitors at the NPA stand were farmers, not to mention scientists and policymakers, who were very interested in the ENVISION tools, comprising four algorithms for: meadow's mowing event detection, minimal soil coverage, crop harvesting event detection and crop type map, with the algorithm accuracy ranging from 94% to 100%.

The ENVISION project attracted a lot of interest in Serbia - at the ENVISION event "Digitalization to increase economic, environmental and social sustainability of agriculture - introduction of new agro-technological solutions" as a part of Biofest. This was a significant milestone for the ENVISION project,

enhancing its visibility, fostering discussions on digitalization in agriculture, and potentially opening up avenues for future collaboration and adoption of its digital solutions in Serbia.

2.9 Policy session – Panta Rhei Conferences

The ENVISION project team actively engaged in two Panta Rhei conferences, one held in Bucharest, Romania, and the other in Ljubljana, Slovenia. During the Bucharest conference in October 2022, the ENVISION team established a booth to showcase and promote the project's objectives and outcomes.

In contrast, during the Ljubljana conference in May 2023, the ENVISION project team co-organized a workshop alongside SPACE4GREEN and MEF4CAP. This collaborative workshop aimed to present and deliberate on solutions emerging from these projects, which could support the current and future requirements of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) monitoring within an automated decision-making system. This participation at Panta Rhei gave the project partners insight into what Paying Agencies need.

ENVISION shared the results of several business cases, including insights from Lithuanian, Cypriot, and Flemish Paying Agencies. These cases highlighted the services and tools employed during a two-year pilot implementation phase. Additionally, SPACE4GREEN explored how cutting-edge technologies, such as Copernicus data, GNSS, and blockchain, could automate CAP and environmental sustainability monitoring processes.

MEF4CAP presented emerging ICT technologies for the agricultural domain and how their utilization could enhance future monitoring and evaluation procedures. The workshop's objective was to glean lessons from the projects and gather feedback from relevant stakeholders, ultimately constructing a roadmap for future developments and solutions in the realm of monitoring and evaluation.

Prior to the workshop, a questionnaire was circulated among Panta Rhei Conference attendees. The workshop attracted over 50 participants and facilitated fruitful discussions. The outcomes of the questionnaire and the workshop were presented at the end of the conference by CAPO.

Importantly, it was widely acknowledged that automated geotagged photo analysis and interpretation represent a significant future need, as voiced by all participants. The ENVISION project team was honoured to take part in the second Panta Rhei conference, where these crucial discussions and collaborations transpired.

2.10 Clustering event

Two Clustering events were organized to discuss solutions to support CAP monitoring and agriculture sustainability, presenting and discussing with other related projects and groups, which helped align the project with current needs and trends.

The 2nd clustering event of ENVISION, “Solutions to Support the Current and Future Needs of CAP Monitoring and Agriculture Sustainability in General”, organised by the Horizon 2020 projects ENVISION, AgriBIT, CALLISTO, SPACE4GREEN and VITIGEOSS, took place on the 30th June 2023.

The event further expanded the connection among European projects dealing with Earth Observation technologies for monitoring farm management activities with regard to sustainability in compliance with CAP. Tangible outcomes in respect to services and best practices were demonstrated; insight to future actions, vision and prospects was presented. EUROGEO Action Group honoured the event with a speech about the future of EO and GEOSS in enhancing CAP.

SOLUTIONS TO SUPPORT THE CURRENT AND FUTURE NEEDS OF CAP MONITORING & AGRICULTURE SUSTAINABILITY IN GENERAL; PRESENTATIONS & DISCUSSION

CLUSTERING EVENT

OBJECTIVES

FRIDAY, 30/6/2023

10:00-12:00 CEST

REGISTRATION LINK
<https://us04web.zoom.us/join/91729055hz-moF4>

This 2nd Clustering event follows and expands the connection among European projects dealing with Earth Observation technologies for monitoring farm management activities with regards to sustainability in compliance with CAP, towards further activating collaboration and complementarity. The event will highlight the tangible outcomes in respect to services and best practices delivered and assessed through several European projects, keeping insight to future actions, vision and prospects.

10:00-10:30 Welcome & Introduction speech (Vasilis Spitadakis, ETAM SA)

Introduction to the European projects and their objectives in relation to EO monitoring & agriculture sustainability

- ENVISION: Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia, AgroApps
- AgriBIT: Giuseppe Vella, Engineering
- CALLISTO: Dafni Delioglani, Draxis
- SPACE4GREEN: Juan Pablo Garcia, Integrasys
- VITIGEOSS: Raimon Fabregat, Eurecat

10:30-11:50 Tangible outcomes from European projects

Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate requirements of CAP
 ENVISION, Aušrius Kučinskas, Head of Direct Support Control Unit, National Paying Agency of Lithuania

GNSS enablers that evolve the farm advisory services to move into efficient Precise Agriculture services
 AgriBIT, Michael Voskakis, Software Engineer, Agenso

CALLISTO: Towards exhaustive CAP monitoring
 CALLISTO, George Choumos, NOA

Sustainable aware industry through a certifiable Environmental Sustainability calculator
 SPACE4GREEN, Emanuel Lekakis, Head of Agriculture Unit, AgroApps

Presentation of the AgriBIT services platform
 AgriBIT, Tommaso Nicoletti, Software Engineer, Engineering

Blockchain and GNSS as traceable solutions that ease and automate the process for managing the CAP from farmers to Public Authorities
 SPACE4GREEN, César Díaz, CAAND

Presentation of VITIGEOSS solution
 VITIGEOSS, Ernesto Batsidas, ELEAF

11:50-12:10 Looking into the future of EO for CAP and agriculture

Advancing Agriculture: The future of EO and GEOSS data in enhancing CAP
 EuroGEO Agriculture Action Group – Stylianos Kotsopoulos

Discussion and Closing Remarks
 Moderated by Vasilis Spitadakis, ETAM SA

Project ENVISION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

Figure 13: Agenda for Clustering event

CLUSTERING EVENT

Solutions to support the current and future needs of CAP monitoring and agriculture sustainability in general; presentation & discussion

FRIDAY, 30/6/2023 📅
10:00-12:00 CEST 🕒

envision AgriBIT CALLISTO SPACE4GREEN VITI6EOSS EuroGEO

Project ENVISION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

The clustering event was filmed, and the record is available on the ENVISION YouTube channel.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E1OLVmYC5cA&t=1138s>

2.11 External events

External events serve for disseminating information about the project, initiating cooperation, and fostering collaboration activities. The ENVISION project partners actively attended these events, including industry fairs, conferences, and meetings, to present the project's activities and results.

ENVISION Consortium actively participated in 21 different external events and thereby exceeded the set KPI.

Table 7: External events attended by ENVISION project partners

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
URDG	06/07/2023	Earth Observation Technologies and Data for African Agriculture	Earth Observation (EO) – including satellite data and drone imaging- is used to support innovation across agriculture and food production, from monitoring weather conditions and improving in-field decisions to managing supply chains. African countries are now developing world-expertise in these technologies.

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>Collaboration between partners in the UK and Africa provides innovation opportunities to address the challenges facing African Agrifood systems. Join us to explore how space technologies can support African AgriFood, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase production through improved accuracy and relevance of decision support tools - Improve supply chain efficiency - Sustainable management of environmental resources and supply chain traceability - Resilience to climate change <p>We have been added to a collaboration database.</p>

2.12 Presentations/attending at International Conferences

The ENVISION project partners actively attended 17 different international conferences to present the project's activities, results, and to engage with the international community.

The ENVISION project's active participation in international conferences has significantly contributed to its visibility, collaboration opportunities, and gathering of valuable insights on a global scale.

2.13 PR articles published in national/regional/European press

PR articles published in national/regional/European press are important dissemination channels for sharing ENVISION results in the community. The KPI for this task was set really high, too high but we did try to do our best and reach 27 published PR articles.

Table 8: PR articles published in national/regional/European press

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Publication document (URL)
ETAM	28/07/2023	Area monitoring in the Common Agricultural Policy ENVISION H2020 project participated in the EU Paying Agencies' Panta	https://neoskopos.com/en/2023/08/04/news/cyprus/envision-h2020-project-presents-solutions-for-area-monitoring-in-common-agricultural-policy-at-eu-conference/

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Publication document (URL)
		Rhei Conference held in Ljubljana, Slovenia	https://farmersreviewafrica.com/area-monitoring-in-the-common-agricultural-policy/ https://www.agribusinessglobal.com/markets/eu-how-area-monitoring-will-support-the-new-common-agricultural-policy/ https://www.agroportal.pt/area-monitoring-in-the-common-agricultural-policy/

2.14 Publications in business journals

Publications in business journals ensure that the project's outcomes are communicated to industry professionals, stakeholders, and other relevant parties.

ENVISION project partners could have made better use of this channel and more actively sought to disseminate its results and findings through publications in reputable business journals, ensuring that its contributions are recognized and utilized by the broader business community.

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Publication document (URL)
INOS	19/09/2023	Projekat ENVISION – nova šansa organičara u Srbiji (ENVISION project - a new chance to the organic producer)	https://www.agromarketsrbija.rs/files/deals/web_130.pdf Pages 45-46

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Publication document (URL)
		<p>Projekat ENVISION – nova šansa organičara u Srbiji</p> <p>Projekat ENVISION je naučno-istraživački projekat međunarodnog karaktera u okviru Inovativnog programa „Horizon 2020“ podržan od strane Evropske unije.</p> <p>Projekat „ENVISION“ ima za cilj unapređenje sektora za agrarna plaćanja i sertifikacionih kuća bazirano na korišćenju satelitskih podataka, kontinuiranim i sistematskim nadgledanjem poljoprivrednog zemljišta, preusmeravajući fokus sa usitnjenog nadzora ograničenog na određena polja i datume, na nadgledanje širom teritorije i tokom cele godine.</p> <p>Pored dve organizacije iz Srbije („Organic Control System“ iz Subotice i „JmoSens“ iz Novog Sada), u projektu učestvuju i četiri organizacije iz Gibrta (AgroAgps, DRAMIS, ETAMI NDA), po dve organizacije iz Velike Britanije (LEAF i University of Reading) i Belgije (UVI i EV ILVO), po jedna organizacija iz Litvanije (NPA), Kijra (CAPO) i Slovenije (TTC), a koje imaju zadatak razvoja sata savremenih IT alata za kontinuirano i sistematsko nadgledanje održivih poljoprivrednih praksi, koji omogućavaju organizacijama koji se bave monitoringom poljoprivrede da se što pre adaptiraju na zahteve koji proizilaze iz novih reformi Evropske unije.</p> <p>Projekat se razvija kroz četiri pilot projekta, od kojih pilot projekat koji se radi u Srbiji ima za cilj poboljšanje celokupnog monitoringa u procesu organske sertifikacije kroz IS tehnologiju i razlikovanje organske od konvencionalne proizvodnje. Kroz četvrti pilot projekat „ENVISION“ će koristiti sve dostupne podatke (iz satelitskih snimaka, od poljoprivrednika i sa terena) i najavarenije tehnologije za pružanje potpuno automatizovane usluge identifikacije useva/magracija vrsta useva koji ima konačno za cilj utvrđivanje da li je određena vrsta useva gijena metodom organske proizvodnje.</p> <p>Projektna aktivnosti se odnose na izradu ENVISION seta alata koji će omogućiti različitim akterima niz servisa za prodavnice oblasti poljoprivrede kroz obrazu</p>	<p>Projekat je institucionalno podržan od strane Ministarstva poljoprivrede, šumarstva i vodoprivrede Republike Srbije jer ovakva vrsta aktivnosti nesumnjivo doprinosi osnaživanju tržišta digitalnih informacija u regionu a i šire, kao i digitalizovanju samog poljoprivrednog sektora Srbije.</p> <p>Sve ovo su dobri razlozi za primenu ENVISION projekta u Srbiji koji pored novih IT rešenja u organskoj poljoprivredi značajno doprinose praćenju kvaliteta proizvoda, a ne samo kvantiteta, uz očuvanje i unapređenje prirodnih resursa što je imperativ današnje organske poljoprivrede ali i poljoprivrede uopšte. Pokazateljci toga su i da firma Organic Control System (OCS) svoje učeske u ENVISION projektu vidi kao ozbiljan izazov za dalji rad u sektoru organske poljoprivrede kroz razvoj novih IT rešenja sa partnerima.</p> <p>Kada je u pitanju IT sektor i organska poljoprivreda nema konačnih znanja i konačnih rešenja, sve je uvek u preispitivanju.</p>

2.15 Scientific and Technical publications

Scientific and Technical publications in an innovation action are secondary to the more commercially-oriented marketing activities of industrial partners. However, they represent an important means of project result dissemination. We expected that at least three scientific papers would be published, targeting academics, researchers and relevant professionals. And the end of the project we had four published publications.

Scientific and technical publications play an important role in ensuring that the project's findings are accessible to a wide range of readers, including researchers, scientists, and experts in the field. Their impact enhances the project's visibility and contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the domain.

2.16 White Papers and Testimonials

White Papers are comprehensive reports designed to provide a detailed understanding of complex issues, presenting the project's philosophy and approach to the matter. They aim to help readers grasp an issue, address a challenge, or make informed decisions.

NOA has crafted three White Papers, the first of which has been presented in D7.3. You can find and read the next two here. The fourth White Paper has been expertly prepared by EV ILVO.

<https://envision-h2020.eu/envision-2-white-paper-grassland-mowing-detection-national-observatory-of-athens/>

White
paper

National Observatory of Athens

**GRASSLAND MOWING
DETECTION**

Contact
Haris Kontoes

Email
kontoes@noa.gr

Revolutionize your grassland management with our advanced Grassland Mowing Events Detection service. This cutting-edge Earth observation change detection module combines satellite data from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 with Deep Learning algorithms to monitor grassland activity using artificially refined vegetation indices at the pixel level. With our service, you can accurately track the dates of mowing events and optimize your operations for maximum productivity and profitability.

Experience the power of technology and take your grassland management to the next level with our sophisticated solution.

KEY FEATURES:

- Accurate Reconstruction of NDVI**
 The service is able to reconstruct the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) based on data from Sentinel-1 satellite, which provides a solution to the challenge of cloud coverage that may obscure data from other satellite sources.
- Mowing Events Identification**
 The service uses the newly created NDVI to identify mowing events in grassland vegetation. This provides an efficient and reliable way of tracking mowing activities that can have significant impacts on the productivity and sustainability of agricultural operations.
- Compliance with National Regulations**
 The results derived from the service can be used to evaluate compliance with national regulations for mowing activities, ensuring that agricultural practices meet legal requirements and environmental standards. This helps to promote sustainable agriculture and support the growth and development of the agricultural sector.

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

**White
paper**

**PAS ADVANTAGES WITH GRASSLAND
MOWING DETECTION:**

- Scalability**
 Our service can be used to monitor mowing events in grasslands at any scale, from small areas to entire countries.
- Constant Direction**
 Our service provides continuous guidance throughout the cultivation period, helping PAs to monitor mowing events in real-time and make informed decisions.
- Performance**
 Our service utilizes advanced Deep Learning algorithms and artificial vegetation indices to accurately detect and track mowing events in grasslands.
- Efficiency**
 Our service allows for the efficient monitoring of mowing events in grasslands, reducing the need for costly manual field visits and inspections.

Grassland Mowing Events Detection

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

Figure 14: The second White Paper provided by NOA

Third White Paper prepared by NOA was published in September.

<https://envision-h2020.eu/envision-3-white-paper-analytics-on-vegetation-and-soil-index-time-series-national-observatory-of-athens/>

White Paper

National Observatory of Athens

ANALYTICS ON VEGETATION AND SOIL INDEX TIME-SERIES

Contact
Haris Kontoes

Email
kontoes@noa.gr

Our innovative product is here to modernize the way agriculture land is monitored, providing valuable insights and automating the process of detecting potential issues. By leveraging advanced analytics and Earth observation data, we have created a comprehensive solution that includes long time series of multiple vegetation indices for monitoring agriculture land at a national scale. Our product offers more than just vegetation indices, delivering additional information and statistics in user-defined areas of interest. It also enables soil monitoring and monitoring of compliance regulations of Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) such as statutory management requirements (SMRs) and good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs).

KEY FEATURES:

- Monitoring of GAECs and SMRs requirements through Incompliance Maps**
 - Proximity to waterways / Runoff Risk assessment for NVAs water pollution
 - Minimum soil cover for Soil Erosion
 - Stubble Burning Identification and Burnt Scar Mapping
- Harvest Events Monitoring and Detection of illegal activity on Natura2000 regions**
- Comprehensive GIS and Analytics Tools**
 - Advanced Visualization of Vegetation Indices
 - Robust Temporal and Zonal Statistics
 - Dynamic Animations of Area Evolution over Time
 - Smart Multi-Faceted Geospatial Queries
 - Accurate Detection of Index Anomalies and Trends

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

envision

White Paper

PAS ADVANTAGES WITH ANALYTICS ON VEGETATION AND SOIL INDEX TIME-SERIES

- Enhanced Monitoring**

Continuous monitoring of vegetation and soil over time.
- Early Detection**

The time-series analysis provides an early warning system for any potential problems.
- Improved Efficiency**

The service helps to reduce the time and resources required for manual data analysis and interpretation.
- Scalability**

The service can be scaled to accommodate small areas of interest as well as large-scale national monitoring programs.
- Customizable Analysis**

The service offers a variety of customizable analysis tools to meet specific needs and requirements.

2022-06-17

2022-06-22

2022-06-27

2022-07-02

Stubble Burning Events Detection

For more information, visit <https://envision-h2020.eu/> and follow us on social media:

ENVISION-H2020

ENVISIONH2020

ENVISIONH2020

ENVISIONH2020

ENVISIONH2020

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

Figure 15: The third White Paper provided by NOA

EV ILVO wrote the White Paper about Monitoring of soil conditions:

<https://envision-h2020.eu/envision-4-white-paper-monitoring-of-soil-conditions/>

**Flemish Research Institute for
Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
(EV ILVO)**

Contact
Panos Ilias

Email
Panos.Ilias@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

MONITORING OF SOIL CONDITIONS

Scientific evidence¹ indicates that about 60 to 70% of soils in the EU are currently in an unhealthy state. Between 61% and 73% of agricultural soils in the EU are affected by erosion, loss of organic carbon, nutrient (nitrogen) exceedances, compaction or secondary salinisation (or a combination of these threats). EV ILVO develops innovative data products that allow soil monitoring using indicators considering soil-pedoclimatic conditions. For the development of the products, EV ILVO uses Copernicus services and available soil points of known measured conditions. The data products can deliver information at a large scale, which means at the regional or national levels, EU-wide. The data products have a high spatial resolution and adequate accuracy to support relevant continuous monitoring. The soil quality information can also be assigned to agricultural parcels when monitoring rural areas to support CAP needs. The delivery of the products can be done directly, using maps or via APIs to support application development on the client side. Current EV ILVO soil monitoring data products estimate indicators that inform on the topsoil organic carbon conditions.

KEY FEATURES AND PAS BENEFITS:

Soil Monitoring framework as a service

The service establishes a monitoring framework that provides the data and information needed to define the right measures at a wide range. The service applies artificial intelligence solutions based on field-based measurements without excluding the use of a sensing system.

Cost-efficient monitoring with sufficient granularity

The service has been designed to provide affordable services with sufficient granularity for monitoring and trend analysis, supporting the definition of the right measures.

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

White Paper

- Adaptation to local conditions considering local districts**
 Our service utilizes advanced Deep Learning algorithms and artificial vegetation indices to The service considers the wide range of soil types, specific local and climatic conditions and the land use or cover. It can be applied to established soil districts across the EU, allowing the reporting using harmonised indicators.
- Continuously research and updates**
 Data products are updated to follow the EU Directives (for example, the Soil Monitoring Law) and National Regulations.
- Different ways to access the data products**
 You may access and use the data products directly by providing GIS maps that visualise the information according to the customer needs or by using Application Programming Interfaces supporting the integration with existing systems or the development of smart applications.
- Transparency on the performance**
 Soil monitoring data products are delivered with their metadata, providing information related to the models' performance and supporting further decision-making. Additionally, applying modern techniques unlocks the hidden information in the models.

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

Figure 16: The fourth White Paper provided by EV ILVO

By publishing white papers, the ENVISION project ensures that its research and methodologies are accessible.

ENVISION testimonials has been filmed by:

- Csilla Nemet, Project Manager (OCS)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c7lcrqDRhHM>

- Abbey Holman, (LEAF)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yraph_UOEul

Aušrius Kučinskas wrote a testimonial:

“My name is Aušrius Kučinskas. I represent the National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture in Lithuania. As the Head of Direct Support Control Unit in this company, I am responsible for the advancement of remote sensing technologies and their practical use within the organization, while monitoring and ensuring the farmers comply with CAP AE-linked requirements.

After learning about the “Envision H2020” project, we decided to get involved in its activities, and it has been a decision we haven't looked back on. Envision's products and services have delivered significant added value, especially in the implementation of the CAP needs, offering a range of benefits that have transformed the way we operate.

The most impressive aspect of Envision's technologies is the accuracy and reliability of the algorithms' results, consistently reaching a remarkably high percentage. This level of precision is instrumental in minimizing errors and uncertainties in our decision-making processes. It is our belief that PAs are highly likely to embrace and extensively use these algorithms at the operational level for checking the implementation of requirements. Envision's solutions have made compliance monitoring more straightforward and reliable than ever before.

In conclusion, the “Envision H2020” project has been a transformative force in our organization and we are proud to be part of this journey. The remarkable benefits of sanctions prevention, reduced workloads, fewer on-site inspections, cost savings and enhanced crop management have had a profound impact on our operations. Envision's unwavering commitment to accuracy and reliability is commendable and we foresee a future where their algorithms become an organization standard for CAP compliance monitoring.”

2.17 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

All partners focus on building up trust and cooperation with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions.

The bulk of the meeting with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions was done in the previous reporting period. In this deliverable, we report the 41. Meeting.

Table 9: Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
EV ILVO	03/05/2023	Plant@lunch on Carbon Farming	The meeting was attended by ILVO and associated departments, highlighting ongoing efforts and initiatives around soil organic carbon. Participants were briefed on the results and took part in deliberations on possible avenues for future cooperation.

3 Outcome of Dissemination Efforts: Commercial Leads and Impact

A multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy was used to maximise the impact of the dissemination activities, carefully adjusting the activities, materials and tools to the specific needs, interests and involvement of the target groups.

From

- the initial phase with approach-oriented content (project presentation, objectives, expected results) to
- the pre-operational phase (creating more targeted awareness regarding techniques towards researchers, industry key players and stakeholders) to
- the maturity phase with a focus on the promotion of concrete results to potential customers,

we successfully landed the potential customers of the ENVISION services and products, presented in the table below.

Table 10: Potential ENVISION customers

Customers	Interest of products	Communication activity
Rural Payment Agency, DEFRA	Soil Organic Carbon	Online meetings
Danish Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries	Soil Organic Carbon	Online meetings
Serbian Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy	Distinction of Organic Farming Practices, Crop Classification	Person-to-person meetings, participation in ENVISION events

German Central Competence Center, State of Management Academy for Food, Agriculture and Forestry	Crop Classification Mowing detection	Online meetings
The Agency For Services and Payment - France	Monitor boundaries especially areas where grasslands and pasturelands meet forests Parcel delineation	Online meetings
Agtelligence - UK	Biodiversity net gain monitoring (environmental protection and sustainable development) Soil Organic Carbon Crop type mapping Soil Erosion	Online meetings
Greek Paying Agency, OPEKEPE	Crop classification, Grassland/ mowing detection, Mobile Application	Person-to-person meetings, participation in ENVISION events
Inspection Institute for Organic Products "BIO Hellas" (BIO)	Distinction of Organic Farming Practices, Crop Classification	Person-to-person meetings, online meetings
Inspection and Certification Organisation TUV Hellas	Distinction of Organic Farming Practices, Crop Classification	Person-to-person meetings, online meetings
Agricultural Chamber – Institute Murska Sobota	Cultivated Crop type maps Analysis on vegetation and soil index time series	Person-to-person meetings, participation in ENVISION events

4 Analysis of results

Based on KPIs identified in the ENVISION D7.1, the progress achieved by the consortium during three years is in the following Table 10.

Table 11: Key Performance Indicators

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achieved from the beginning of the project until the end
C1 Envision website	Numbers of visits to the project website	10.000	32.282 Visitors 59. 522 Page views
C2 A commercial mini-site (redesign of the ENVISION website)	A commercial mini-site	1	1
C3 Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, SlideShare)	Followers on Social Media	1.200	1104
	Posts on social networks relevant to the project	1.200	713
C4 Animation video	Animation video	1	2
C5 ENVISION e-Newsletters	Recipients of project e-newsletters	5.000	88 Mailchimp 713 ENVISION social media 3000 DIH Social Media
C6 ENVISION promotional material	Brochure and leaflets	3.000	2020 printed leaflets
	Roll-up and poster	1 and 1	1 and 1
C7 EuroGEOSS showcase	Expression of interest signed by EuroGEOSS and ENVISION LP	1	1
C8 Hackathon	Hackathon	1	1
C9 Meetings with developers, open-source communities	Meetings with developers, open-source communities	10	12
C10 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	80	39
C11 Policy session	Policy session	1	1
C12 Project events (seminars/workshops)	Project events	8	13
C13 Clustering events/workshops	Clustering events/workshops	2	2
C14 External events	External events	15	21
C15 Presentation/attending at International Conferences	Presentation/attending at International Conferences	20	17

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achieved from the beginning of the project until the end
C16 PR articles published in national/regional/European press	PR articles published in national/regional/European press	100	27
C17 Publications in business journals	Publications in business journals	10	2
C18 Scientific and Technical publications	Publication	3	4
C19 White papers and testimonials	White papers and testimonials	6 White papers and testimonials	5 White Papers 4 Video Testimonials
C20 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	40	41

5 Conclusions

The ENVISION project has undertaken a series of significant activities over its duration. WP7 has delivered all of the required tasks and deliverables. ENVISION project partners have made significant strides in their objectives, actively engaged with stakeholders and disseminated their findings.

Dissemination included a wide range of traditional information channels, such as project leaflet, newsletters, social media posts and news publications regarding the project, but also through the partners' own channels.

Key among these has been the establishment and regular updating of the ENVISION website, which serves as the primary interface for communication with the public.

In addition to the website, the project has actively engaged with the public through various social media channels, including LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and SlideShare. Data from these channels indicates a consistent increase in followers, suggesting that the content published resonates with the target audience.

The distribution of e-newsletters was an effective tool for keeping stakeholders informed and engaged with the project's progress and outcomes.

Numerous meetings and active participation took place in virtual settings, minimizing the need for physical travel among project partners. Travel was primarily reserved for significant project events. In a particularly efficient move, we strategically synchronized the third project meeting with the Panta Rhei conference in Ljubljana. This approach allowed us to maximize our time and engagement while reducing unnecessary travel.

Participation in the EuroGEOSS showcase and Panta Rhei allowed for presenting project outcomes and networking with relevant stakeholders.

The initial work carried out to set the dissemination plan and identify stakeholders put the ENVISION project on a good path to success from the dissemination perspective.

The project set specific KPIs to measure the success of various activities. Some targets were exceeded, others were not fully met, indicating areas for improvement in future projects.

The diverse range of tasks and activities collectively contributed to its success. These efforts facilitated knowledge dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and the establishment of a solid foundation for future collaborations and applications of the project's outcomes.

All this range of tasks and activities contributed significantly to the project's overall impact. The project's impact was evident in its ability to reach a wide audience, share valuable insights, and foster meaningful connections.

ENVISION partners are willing to continue disseminating the project results beyond the project lifetime to ensure better sustainability and usability of the project results.

End of Document

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869366.